

Early Colonialism in Africa and Asia: Liberation Movements and the Legacy

Dr Poulami Aich Mukherjee

Assistant Professor, Postgraduate Department of History and Research Centre

Assumption College Autonomous, Changanassery, Kerala

Abstract

‘Colonialism’ has been perhaps one of the most discussed themes of academia since the time of its inception as an ideology due to its complex, diverse and multiple variants has been evolved in different stages in human history. Colonialism is arguably the most important force integrating different indigenous societies into the world systems of capitalism and the nation state particularly in Africa and Asia. Although large geographic portions of Africa and Asia achieved formal independence from European colonial powers between 1945 and 1999, the systems of nationalism and capitalism that colonialism set in motion continued to create power imbalances that favored the economies and militaries of historic colonial powers. For this reason, many anti-colonial activists in the twenty-first century consider decolonization to be an unfinished process blocked by neocolonial economic relations. The present paper is an attempt to understand the nuances of earliest colonial and imperial ventures in Africa and Asia, nature of the ‘colony’ and the process of socio-cultural-political penetration, resistance movements and liberation and the post-liberation developments leading to the Afro-Asian solidarity.

Keywords: Colonialism, Colonization, Resistant Movements, Liberation, Post-liberation developments

Introduction

The history of early colonialism in Africa and Asia is marked by the rise of European powers in the 16th and 17th centuries, which would eventually lead to the establishment of extensive colonial empires. These empires shaped the political, social, and economic landscapes of both continents for centuries. However, they also laid the groundwork for powerful liberation movements in the 19th and 20th centuries, as colonized peoples fought for independence and self-determination. The legacies of these movements and the colonial experience still resonate today.

The term ‘colonialism’ has been described and defined in multiple ways. The Encyclopedia Britannica (2010) refers to colonialism as, ‘...the exercise of political and economic sovereignty by a country on a country or territory outside its borders...’. The Macmillan Family Encyclopedia (1991) refers to it as ‘...a system of control by a country over a dependent area or people outside its borders’. Further in elucidating European Colonialism, it places its fingers on ‘economic aims’ and

‘the economic policies of Mercantilism’.¹

Likewise, The World Book Encyclopedia (1993) describes colonialism as, ‘the rule of a group of people by a foreign power. The people and their land make up a colony. Most colonies are separated from the ruling nation by an ocean. The foreign power sends members of its own populace to live in the colony, to govern it, and to use it as a source of wealth. The rulers and the local people usually belong to different ethnic groups.’²

The idea of ‘Colonialism’ is often connected with the concept of ‘Imperialism’. Edward Said in Culture and Imperialism (1994) differentiates Colonialism and Imperialism as: ‘imperialism’ means the practice, the theory, and the attitude of the dominating metropolitan center ruling a distant territory; ‘colonialism’, which is almost always a consequence of imperialism, is the implanting of settlements on distant territory. The World Book Encyclopedia (1993) defines imperialism as ‘the policy or action by which one country controls another country’s territory. Most of such control is achieved by military means to obtain economic and political advantages’.³

Another word to discuss this policy is ‘Expansionism’. J. D. Hargreaves (1993) defines imperialism as ‘The use of state power in order to advance national interests and to exercise control over weaker people’ and further defines Economic Imperialism as, ‘The influence exercised by capital enterprises in less developed part of the world’. However, the issue of colonization as a process marks its beginning with the settlements of the European societies across the world in the form of colonies. Here, it may be gainful to discuss the various types of colonies for further reference.⁴

Colonialism did not manifest itself in the same mode of settlements or establishments of colonies over the world. Broadly, the various types of colonies that have been identified include Settler Colonies, Dependencies, Plantation Colonies and Trading Posts. These definitions bring out the important aspect of colonialism: the human attitude and behavior which has attempted to incur into ‘others’ space and explore and exploit the belongings of ‘others’. The historical facts reveal that around ¾th of the world was under the colonial yoke of the European powers for the last 500 years or so, some nations for a shorter duration while some others for a longer period of time. This process of colonization ushered in changes in almost every realm of human existence of the colonized lands. Of these, India and Africa are two geo- political entities which had gone through life altering experiences. Although richly endowed both in terms of resources and culture, they were left impoverished and undermined by the experience of colonialism under the colonial regimes. This social alienation and suppression of the native populace by the colonizers resulted in a society divided on the grounds of religion, race and colour.⁵

The situations as seen in the African nations did not arise in India in the post-colonial era. In India, this could be credited to diverse cultural heritage, high standard of literary evolution, both written and oral, use of English as the ‘lingua franca’ by the elite groups though not at the cost of erasing the regional languages, which have survived and grown. Further India has been a culturally developed society even prior to colonization. Further, the adoption of a democratic model of a republic and the formation of states on the basis of languages after independence has been of great help to sustain and nurture regional ethos, identities and curtailment of centrist hegemony to a large extent.

The case is found to be different with Africa, as the creative output has been predominantly through ‘orature’ or folk literature is a genre of literature that is spoken or sung in contrast to that which is written and the language of the colonizer has come to be accepted as the dominant language of education, politics, diplomacy, etc. The local native language, which has been the carrier of culture and tradition, was slowly sidelined and made non-functional.⁶

Early Colonialisms: Historic Empires

The Portuguese excelled in exploration and trade for centuries. The country's former colonies spread across continents, have varying areas, populations, geographies, histories, and cultures. The Portuguese tremendously affected their colonies politically, economically, and socially. The empire has been criticized for being exploitative, neglectful, and racist. Some colonies still suffer from high poverty and instability, but their valuable natural resources, combined with current diplomatic relations with and assistance from Portugal, may improve the living conditions of these numerous countries. The Portuguese language will always be an important connector of these countries and a reminder of how vast and significant the Portuguese empire once was.⁷

Portugal is noted as the first modern European country to have large numbers of black slaves. As one of the major sea powers of the fifteenth, sixteenth, and seventeenth centuries, Portugal also shipped and sold large numbers of African slaves to other parts of the world. Not surprisingly, the issue of slavery has shaped racial tensions between Portugal and Africa. It dominated Portuguese colonialist practices and prompted Africans to hold hostile attitudes toward the Portuguese. Other offensive colonialist practices also complicated race relations between blacks and whites in the Portuguese colonies of Angola, Mozambique, Guinea-Bissau, São Tomé and Príncipe, and Cape Verde. The Portuguese created colonies for numerous reasons:⁸

- To trade for spices, gold, agricultural products, and other resources
- To create more markets for Portuguese goods
- To spread Catholicism
- To ‘civilize’ the natives of these distant places

Portugal's colonies brought great wealth to this small country. But the empire gradually declined, as it did for other colonizers, partly because Portugal did not have enough people or resources to maintain so many overseas territories. A move for independence among the colonies finally sealed its fate. Here are the most important former Portuguese possessions:

Brazil was by far Portugal's largest colony by area and population. It was reached by the Portuguese in 1500 and was part of the Treaty of Tordesillas, signed with Spain in 1494, allowing Portugal claim over Brazil. The Portuguese imported enslaved Africans and forced them to grow sugar, tobacco, cotton, coffee, and other cash crops. The Portuguese also extracted Brazil wood from the rainforest, which was used to dye European textiles. They also helped to explore and settle the vast interior of Brazil. In the 19th century, the royal court of Portugal lived in and governed both Portugal and Brazil from Rio de Janeiro.⁹

Brazil gained independence from Portugal in 1822. In the 1500s, Portugal colonized the present-day West African country of Guinea-Bissau and the two southern African countries of Angola and Mozambique. The Portuguese captured and enslaved many people from these countries and sent them to the New World. Gold and diamonds were also extracted from these colonies. In the 20th century, Portugal was under international pressure to release its colonies, but Portugal's dictator, Antonio Salazar, refused to decolonize.¹⁰

Several independence movements in these three African countries erupted into the Portuguese Colonial War of the 1960s and 1970s, which killed tens of thousands and was associated with communism and the Cold War. In 1974, a military coup in Portugal forced Salazar out of power, and the new government of Portugal ended the unpopular and expensive war. Angola, Mozambique, and Guinea-Bissau gained independence in 1975. All three countries were underdeveloped, and civil wars in the decades after independence took millions of lives. More than a million refugees from these three countries immigrated to Portugal after independence and strained the Portuguese economy. Cape Verde and Sao Tome and Principe, two small archipelagos located off the western coast of Africa, were also colonized by the Portuguese. Sao Tome and Principe are two small islands making up a single country. They were uninhabited before the Portuguese arrived and were used in the slave trade. They both achieved independence from Portugal in 1975.¹¹

In the 1500s, the Portuguese colonized the western Indian region of Goa. Goa, located on the Arabian Sea, was an important port in spice-rich India. In 1961, India annexed Goa from the Portuguese and it became an Indian state. Goa has many Catholic adherents in primarily Hindu India. The Portuguese also colonized the eastern half of the island of Timor in the 16th century. In 1975, East Timor declared independence from Portugal, but the island was invaded and annexed by Indonesia. East Timor became independent in 2002. In the 16th century, the Portuguese colonized

Macau, on the South China Sea. Macau served as an important Southeast Asian trading port. The Portuguese empire ended when Portugal handed over control of Macau to China in 1999.

Liberation Movements: origins and impacts

European colonialism in Africa intensified during the late 19th century, culminating in what is often called the ‘Scramble for Africa’. European powers, such as Britain, France, Germany, Belgium, and Italy, partitioned the continent at the Berlin Conference (1884–1885) without regard for existing ethnic, cultural, or political boundaries. This led to the creation of arbitrary colonial borders that would later fuel conflicts. Britain and France were the dominant colonial powers, with Britain establishing control over regions such as Egypt, Sudan, Kenya, and South Africa, while France took much of West and Central Africa, including Algeria, Senegal, and Mali. The methods of control varied but often included military conquest, settler colonization, and the establishment of extractive economies that exploited local resources. Colonized African societies were forced into labor systems such as forced labor, taxation, and crop production for export, often at the expense of subsistence farming. This led to widespread economic inequality and social discontent, prompting early resistance movements. Even before the major independence movements of the 20th century, African societies resisted colonial domination. Notable examples include: The Maji Maji Rebellion (1905–1907) which was a significant uprising against German colonial rule in present-day Tanzania. The Anglo-Zulu War (1879), in which the Zulu forces resisted British annexation in southern Africa. The Mahdist Revolt (1881–1899) was an Islamic uprising against British-Egyptian control in Sudan.¹²

British colonization of India began in the 17th century through the East India Company but formally took control in 1858 after the Indian Rebellion of 1857, the Sepoy Mutiny which was a massive, though unsuccessful, and attempt at liberation. The British Raj established deep political, economic, and social control over India, transforming it into a key part of the British Empire. India's vast agricultural and mineral resources were systematically extracted to benefit Britain, while industrial development in India was stunted to keep it as a colonial supplier of raw materials. Additionally, British policies created significant famines, with millions of deaths.¹³

The British implemented policies that suppressed traditional Indian institutions and cultures, which contributed to long-term resentment. They also divided communities along religious and ethnic lines, fostering tensions that would later fuel conflicts post-independence. The Dutch established control over what is now Indonesia in the 17th century, beginning with the spice trade. The colonial administration was characterized by a harsh system of forced labor (known as the Cultivation System), which extracted resources like sugar and coffee for export. Similar to the British in India, the Dutch used Indonesia's natural wealth for their own economic benefit, leaving

the indigenous population impoverished. The social and political systems of indigenous societies were also restructured to favor Dutch interests.¹⁴

Resistance to Dutch rule in Indonesia began almost immediately after the arrival of the Europeans, with movements such as the Aceh War (1873–1914) and the growing influence of nationalist ideologies in the early 20th century. France colonized large parts of Southeast Asia, including Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia, during the 19th century. The French controlled the region through heavy military and economic domination, exploiting the land's resources, particularly rubber, rice, and minerals, and establishing a system of forced labour. The French imposed land taxes and took large swathes of agricultural land, pushing peasants into poverty. Education was also used as a tool for control, with a system designed to create a French-speaking elite but leaving the majority of the population uneducated. Nationalist sentiments began to stir in Indochina, especially in Vietnam, where figures like Ho Chi Minh emerged as leaders of anti-colonial movements.¹⁵

In the 1950s and 1960s, three factors helped to bring about a change in traditional Portuguese colonialism. A general anti-colonialist sentiment bubbled up as the result of economic and political developments in Europe in the wake of World War II. France and Great Britain granted independence to almost all of their African colonies. Portugal, forced to defend its presence in Africa, introduced some nominal reforms. In 1951 it also re-categorized its African colonies as Portuguese provinces to block any intervention efforts by the United Nations. Meanwhile, armed revolts led by Africans offered blacks an alternative to the acceptance of Portuguese domination. Portugal introduced more reforms in response to the revolts. And finally, in the 1960s, industrial interests began to compete for the dominant political role that agrarians in Portugal had long held. The need for a less restricted economy, new labor techniques, and increased productivity demanded changes both at home and in the formerly inflexible economic and social structures of the colonies.¹⁶

The liberation movements gained recruits in the 1960s. Large numbers of white settlers, however, wanted to remain under Portuguese control. They even helped to develop a rationale for continued imperial control: The whites argued that Portugal had established a nonracial form of cooperation with the Africans, unlike the racist apartheid regimes in British Africa. They asserted that the races socialized, worked, and married, creating a unique Luso-tropical civilization. While the Portuguese were clearly not as obsessed with race as the South Africans and Rhodesians, Portuguese Africa did not exactly qualify as a colour-blind paradise. Africans and Creoles remained trapped in poverty and at the mercy of a repressive police state designed to crush any attempts at rebellion.¹⁷

The Portuguese treatment of people of colour led to the formation of several organizations that sought independence for Portugal's African colonies. Liga Africana, founded in 1919, joined black and Mulatto students to work for the freedom of Angola, Guinea-Bissau, and Mozambique. It

was short-lived. African liberation movements did not flourish until the 1960s. In Angola, armed resistance began in 1960. Several rioting broke out among the farmers in Malanje province over low crop prices that had been set up by the government. About seven thousand protesters were killed in clashes with police. The Bakongo, along with the Ovimbundu and Kimbundu, form the major indigenous ethnic groups in Angola. The Bakongo took the lead in pushing for autonomy, with the Ovimbundu more closely aligned with white employers, while the Kimbundu were resented by other groups for their control of the job market in the ports. In 1960 the police arrested an *assimilado*, Agostinho Neto, who led the Kimbundu-based Popular Movement for the Liberation of Angola (MPLA). His arrest set off riots in Luanda. In an unrelated development, the Bakongo, led by the Union of the Peoples of Northern Angola later the National Liberation Front in Angola or FNLA under Holden Roberto, rose up in rebellion in 1960 with almost twenty thousand Bakongo killed.¹⁸

In 1961 hundreds of blacks in Luanda protested police brutality by storming the prisons and freeing political prisoners along with ordinary criminals. The city's whites responded by killing hundreds of unarmed blacks. This last event marks the official beginning of Angola's war of liberation. Subsequently, ethnic conflicts damaged the cause of Angolan independence. In 1966 Jonas Savimbi, an Ovimbundu, created the National Union for the Total Independence of Angola (UNITA) to counter the ethnic exclusiveness of FNLA. In Mozambique, armed resistance began in 1964. However, there were several wildcat strikes by African workers in Mozambican ports in the 1950s followed in 1960 by a massive protest by farmers angry about low prices set by government-controlled marketing boards. The *assimilados* led the rebellion. In 1962 they formed the Liberation Front of Mozambique (Frelimo) under Eduardo Mondlane. Frelimo relied upon guerilla tactics. In response, the Portuguese moved many Africans and Creoles into resettlement camps where they could not assist Frelimo. In São Tomé and Príncipe, the Batepá Massacre of 1953 led to the death of several hundred African workers in fighting with Portuguese authorities. In the late 1950s, a small group of São Tomeans formed the Movement for the Liberation of São Tomé and Príncipe (MLSTP). Meanwhile, in Guinea-Bissau, the pan-Africanist Amilcar Cabral joined several others in 1956 to form the African Party for the Independence of Guinea and Cape Verde (PAIGC). Guerilla fighting began in earnest in 1962.¹⁹

The efforts to suppress rebellions in its African colonies put too much stress on the government of Portugal and its dictator, Marcelo Caetano. With the government nearly bankrupt, he was overthrown in April 1974. Among the first decisions made by the leftist coup leaders was to rid Portugal of its overseas possessions as quickly as possible. The decolonization process in the aftermath of the April 1974 revolution in Portugal produced dramatic results, particularly in Angola and Mozambique. Most of the Portuguese population suddenly fled from these countries. The

movement happened more rapidly and dramatically in the case of Angola because of the armed clashes among liberation movements with the support of foreign armies. Both the MPLA in Angola and the Frelimo in Mozambique and, to a lesser extent, the PAIGC in Guinea-Bissau and Cape Verde and the MLSTP in São Tomé and Príncipe encouraged this exodus, under the assumption that most of the settler communities would react against further moves toward the creation of a socialist state, redistribution of wealth, or a centrally planned economy. These radical policies only strengthened the settler communities' feelings against the installation of a black government. In Mozambique, when about 180,000 of the 200,000 Portuguese in the country fled, they spitefully destroyed much of the country's infrastructure before they left.²⁰

The PAIGC declared the independence of Guinea-Bissau on September 24, 1973. Guinea-Bissau would be wracked by civil war until the end of the century. On June 25, 1975, Portugal formally surrendered power in Mozambique. While the country had fewer internal ethnic conflicts than Angola, it also faced danger in the form of white-dominated neighboring Rhodesia. Many former Portuguese colonists from Mozambique now living in Rhodesia supported the terrorist Mozambique National Resistance (Renamo). Fighting between Frelimo and Renamo shook Mozambique until a 1992 peace settlement. São Tomé and Príncipe achieved independence on July 12, 1975. The country subsequently enjoyed peace, democracy, and multiparty elections. Angola achieved formal independence on November 11, 1975. The FNLA had largely collapsed with the MPLA in control of most of the country. UNITA retreated to rural areas in southern and central Angola. Ethnic conflicts continued to ravage the country into the next century. The exaltation of colonialism as national glory was one of the ideological marks of the Estado Novo. Anchored in Gilberto Freyre's Luso-tropicalism, a theory that, in the words of historian Cláudia Castelo, granted 'the Portuguese a special capacity to adapt to the tropics, as a result of their desire for *mestizaje*, for the interpenetration of cultures and for ecumenism.'

Furthermore, he saw in Portuguese colonialism a natural benevolence, derived from its 'fraternal Christianity,' and attributed to the Portuguese peoples and other colonies (including Brazil) a spirit of cultural unity.²¹

In 1961, an attack claimed by the MPLA on the Luanda prison triggered a series of events that started the colonial war, or war of liberation, for African libertarian movements. The war would last until April 25, 1974, and its end was the main motivation for the military revolt that would overthrow the dictatorship, resulting in the Carnation Revolution. But the Portuguese did not fight alone: between 1961 and 1973, the Portuguese Armed Forces recruited thousands of African soldiers, integrating them into its contingents, and working hard in anti-subversion efforts. The war effort for Portugal had an impact on multiple levels: about 90 per cent of the young male population

was mobilized for war, intensifying a wave of emigration that would only slow down after democracy was implemented. In the occupied territories, the massacres lasted until the end of the war. After the withdrawal of Portuguese troops, several countries plunged into civil wars, but it is important to underline that the liberation struggle of the African peoples against Portuguese colonialism was the greatest catalyst for the end of fascism in Portugal. The colonial war caused around 10,000 deaths and 20,000 invalids among Portuguese soldiers and over 100,000 victims among African civilians. The trauma lasts until today for thousands of Portuguese, Africans and their descendants. Hence, the space of joint memory of the colonial war is advanced by some specialists, such as Miguel Cardina or Fátima da Cruz Rodrigues, as a field of reconciliation between peoples.²²

Legacies of Liberation Movements in Asia and Africa

Though liberation and self-determination are universal phenomena, each nation encounters them in its own particular way. Manifestation of nationalism differs widely according to regions, history, cultural traditions and social structure. All these factors play a significant role in shaping the nature of national consciousness. Scholars may agree that ‘nationalism’ as an ideology asserts itself in three stages. Stirrings are the first stage wherein the nation becomes aware of itself as a nation suffering from oppression. With this political awareness people begin to refute alien myths notions and foreign ways. It is the period that seeks to revive the local cultural identity by casting away the imposed identity of foreign rule. In the second stage of nationalism the politically conscious people raise the banner of struggle to achieve independence from the colonial rule. Acts of peaceful protest, demonstrations and violent manifestation of anger against foreigners is expressed very vitally in this stage. The third stage of nationalism involves consolidation of the nation’s self-respect. If one analyzes Goa’s independence struggle based on these three stages it is realized that the socio-religious movements that promoted cultural revivalism formed a part of the first stage of nationalism which was followed by the actual struggle for independence that was launched with violent as well as non-violent methods. The third stage of Goan nationalism began with the Indian independence. India’s attempt to consolidate itself by integrating the princely states and liberating the remaining Indian territories from the French and the Portuguese hold aimed to maintain the national unity of the country.²³

It may be pointed out here that, Pan-Africanism, a movement aimed at uniting African nations against colonialism, with leaders like Kwame Nkrumah (Ghana), Julius Nyerere (Tanzania), and Patrice Lumumba (Congo) playing significant roles. Many African nations employed both nonviolent and violent means to achieve independence. The Algerian War of Independence (1954–1962) against French colonial rule and the Mau Mau Uprising (1952–1960) in Kenya are prominent examples of armed resistance. Meanwhile, figures like Nelson Mandela in South Africa promoted

nonviolent resistance before eventually turning to armed struggle under the African National Congress. India's independence movement, led by figures like Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru, was largely nonviolent. Gandhi's philosophy of nonviolent resistance (Satyagraha) was central to India's struggle, culminating in independence from Britain in 1947. Led by Sukarno and others, Indonesia fought for its independence from the Dutch, which it achieved in 1949 after a bloody struggle. Vietnam's struggle against French colonialism led by the Viet Minh, under Ho Chi Minh, culminated in the defeat of the French at Dien Bien Phu (1954). However, the subsequent division of Vietnam led to the Vietnam War (1955–1975) against American intervention.²⁴

Many newly independent nations faced political instability as colonial borders often ignored ethnic, tribal, and cultural divisions. In Africa, the legacy of artificial borders and a lack of unified national identities contributed to civil wars and conflicts, such as in the Congo, Nigeria, and Sudan.

In Asia, the division of regions like India and Vietnam led to violent partitioning and war. Post-colonial states struggled with economic dependency on former colonial powers and the effects of extractive economies. Many African and Asian countries were left with economies centered on resource extraction with little diversification or industrial development, which hindered long-term economic growth. Colonial rule had profound effects on indigenous cultures, languages, and traditions. While many nations embraced their colonial language such as English, French, or Dutch as a unifying factor, it often led to the erosion of native languages and cultures. Moreover, colonialism's emphasis on racial hierarchies had long-lasting impacts on social relations. Despite formal independence, many former colonies continued to face neo-colonialism, where economic and political dependence on former colonial powers persisted. This struggle for true sovereignty and identity remains a key theme in the post-colonial world.

Conclusion

Scholars such as Walter Rodney argue that European powers pursued colonialism primarily to extract resources and wealth, draining African and Asian economies to fuel European industrialization. Postcolonial theorists like Edward Said emphasize that colonialism was driven by geopolitical rivalries among European nations, as well as a desire to project imperial power. Mahmood Mamdani highlights how colonial administrations exploited ethnic and religious divisions to consolidate control. Franz Fanon underscores the psychological effects of colonialism, which imposed European cultural dominance while devaluing indigenous traditions and self-worth.

African scholars like Basil Davidson highlight anti-colonial uprisings, such as the Maji Maji Rebellion in East Africa and the Sepoy Rebellion in India, as examples of early organized resistance to colonial rule. Amilcar Cabral and other revolutionary thinkers emphasize that anti-colonial movements gained momentum after WWII, as colonial powers were weakened and local elites

became more organized. Scholars like Benedict Anderson argue that nationalism became a powerful force uniting disparate groups against colonial powers. Many liberation leaders, such as Ho Chi Minh in Vietnam and Julius Nyerere in Tanzania, drew from Marxist theories to frame their struggles as part of a global fight against imperialism and capitalism. Walter Rodney argues in *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa* that colonialism deliberately stunted economic growth in colonized regions, creating dependency on European markets.

While some scholars acknowledge infrastructure development under colonialism, they argue that it was designed to benefit colonial exploitation rather than local needs. Crawford Young argues that colonial borders and administrative systems imposed artificial boundaries that undermined postcolonial state stability. Scholars such as Mahmood Mamdani note that colonial governance structures centralized, coercive, and exclusionary often persisted in post-independence regimes. Postcolonial theorists like Homi Bhabha explore the cultural hybridity that emerged under colonial rule, resulting in complex identities among colonized peoples. Franz Fanon in *The Wretched of the Earth* examines the psychological scars left by colonialism, including feelings of inferiority and the internalization of colonial values.

The early colonial period in Africa and Asia set the stage for powerful liberation movements that would reshape both continents in the 20th century. These movements sought to dismantle the economic, political, and cultural systems imposed by colonial powers. While many of these struggles led to independence, the colonial legacy manifested in economic dependency, political instability, and cultural upheaval continues to affect these regions today. The story of early colonialism, and the liberation movements that followed, is a testament to the resilience of colonized peoples and their ongoing fight for justice, equality, and self-determination.

It may be argued here that Colonialism as an ideology worked as a catalyst of creating solidarity among nations with shared colonial pasts. Liberation movements provided strong foundations for the formations of nation-states, nationhood, ideals of nationalisms and human rights. At the same time oriented the nations across the world with the processes of accommodations, assimilations and acculturations which paved the ways for the contemporary globalized world. North of the south and south of the north, an empire with a 'colonial economy', a country that was both the 'source of migrations' and the 'destiny of immigrations', Portugal and Portuguese identity has always been very difficult to define. Being the origin of an empire whose evaluation is still polemic, the Portuguese have been seen in very different ways by their European contemporaries and as well as their colonial counterparts.

Reflections of the legacies of resistance movements are found in the literatures and archaeological remains of Asia and Africa. Most post-colonial and post-modernist formulation of

nations-states, certainly those that emerged with the collapse and shrinking of western colonial empires in Asia and Africa, mid twentieth century onwards, necessarily retrospect on imperialism in an attempt to draw out the asymmetrical relationship of interdependence, past and present, between the materially advanced colonizing powers and themselves especially in the former's hegemonic ascendancy. These articulations, discursive and at times engagingly political, contextualize the multidimensional and ever growing complexities within colonial societies in their engagement with the construction of a cohesive political community.

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